

Existence and uniqueness result for an abstract nonlinear volterra integrodifferential equation

Rupesh T. More

Department of Mathematics,
Arts, Commerce and Science College, Bodwad, Dist.Jalgaon-425 310, India

Corresponding author: Rupesh T. More

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we study the existence, uniqueness and other properties of solutions of an abstract nonlinear volterra integrodifferential equation with nonlocal condition. The tool employed in the analysis is based on application of new three steps iteration. New three steps iteration method has equally important contribution to study various properties such as dependence on initial data, closeness of solutions and dependence on parameters and functions involved therein. A new three steps iteration process introduced by V. Karakaya, Y. Atalan, K. Dogan, and NH. Bouzara (Karakaya et al., 2017).

Keywords: Existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependence; volterra integrodifferential equation, abstract differential equation with finite delay; new three steps iteration method.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of the present paper is to study existence, uniqueness and qualitative properties of mild solutions of nonlinear delay volterra integrodifferential equation with nonlocal condition. The main tools employed in the analysis are based on the applications new three steps equation Method. Using Tychonov's fixed point theorem, the method of successive approximations, and the comparison method, S. Sugiyama (Sugiyama 1960) studied the existence and uniqueness of solutions of the following problem:

$$\frac{d\theta(t)}{dt} = f(t, \theta(t), \theta(t-1)), \quad (1.1)$$

for $0 \leq t \leq t_1$, with the conditions

$$\theta(t-1) = \phi(t) \quad (0 \leq t < 1), \quad (1.2)$$

$$\theta(0) = \theta_0, \tag{1.3}$$

where θ and f represent n -dimensional vectors (see Sugiyama 1960 for details) and Stokes 1960, More 2024, and More 2025 has discussed the similar problems as above for nonlinear differential equations.

From the above works, we can see a fact, although the delay integrodifferential problems have been investigated by some authors. However, to our knowledge, the difference-integrodifferential equation with nonlocal conditions and an infinitesimal generator of operators has not been discussed extensively. So motivated by all the works above, the aim of this paper is to prove the existence and uniqueness of solutions of the difference-integrodifferential of the form:

$$\theta'(t) + A\theta(t) = f(t, \theta(t), \int_0^t \psi(s, \theta(s))ds, \theta(t-1)), \tag{1.4}$$

for $t \in J = [0, b]$, ($b > 1$) under the conditions

$$\theta(t-1) = \phi(t) \quad (0 \leq t < 1), \tag{1.5}$$

$$\theta(0) + g(\theta) = \theta_0, \tag{1.6}$$

where $-A$ is an infinitesimal generator of a strongly continuous semigroup of bounded linear operators $T(t)$ in X , $f \in C(J \times X \times X, X)$, $g \in C(C(J, X), X)$ and $\phi(t)$ is a continuous function for $0 \leq t < 1$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 1-0} \phi(t)$ exists, for which we denote by $\phi(1-0) = c_0$. If we consider the solutions of (1.4) for $t \in J$, we obtain a function $x(t-1)$ which is unable to define as solution for $0 \leq t < 1$. Hence, we have to impose some condition, for example the condition (1.5). We note that, if $0 \leq t < 1$, the problem is reduced to integrodifferential equation

$$\theta'(t) + A\theta(t) = f(t, \theta(t), \int_0^t \psi(s, \theta(s))ds, \phi(t)),$$

with initial condition $\theta(0) + g(\theta) = \theta_0$. Here, it is essential to obtain the solutions of (1.4)–(1.6) for $0 \leq t \leq b$, so that, we suppose in the sequel b is not less than 1.

The development of integral and differential equations and their advantages in science and applied mathematics are largely attributed to the notion of fixed points theory of iterative approximation (TIA) (Morante and Roach 2008, Tidke and Patil 2023, Tidke et al., 2023). In this

regard, for specific classes of operators, a lot of researchers has found several iteration techniques in terms of their convergence, rate of convergence, equivalence of convergence etc. (Agarwal, et al., 2007 and Soltuz and Grosan 2008). A number of mathematicians have studied the challenges of existence, uniqueness, and other properties of solutions of particular forms of IVP (1.4)-(1.6) and its variants under a set of hypotheses via various tactics (Sahu, 2011; Dobritoiu, 2008; Dobritoiu, 2012; Berinde, 2010; Karakaya et al., 2017; Atalan & Karakaya, 2017; Atalan, Gursoy, & Khan, 2021) and some of the references cited therein (Pazy, 1983; Webb, 1978; Tidke, 2011; Tidke & Patil, 2023; Tidke & More, 2014; Byszewski, 1991; Dhakne & Tidke, 2009; Martin, 1976; More, 2025; Soltuz & Grosan, 2008; Sugiyama, 1960; Stokes, 1960).

Our main objective here is to investigate the existence and uniqueness of the solutions solution to (1.4)-(1.6).

We present the preliminaries and hypotheses, in section 2 deals with existence and uniqueness of the solution, we discuss result on continuous dependency on initial data, on function, on parameter.

Preliminaries and hypotheses.

Before proceeding to main results, we recall some basic definitions, preliminaries and related hypotheses.

Three Steps Iteration Process:

Karakaya et al., (2017) introduced the following three steps iteration process:

$$\begin{cases} \theta_{k+1} &= Ty_k, \\ y_k &= (1 - \xi_k)z_k + \xi_k Tz_k, \\ z_k &= T\theta_k, \quad k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}. \end{cases} \quad (1.7)$$

with the real control sequence $\{\xi_k\}_0^\infty \in [0, 1]$ satisfying $\sum_{k=0}^\infty \xi_k = \infty$.

Definition 1.1 ([22], p.627) Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a weak-contraction for which there exist $\delta \in (0,1)$ and $L \geq 0$ such that

$$\|T\theta - Ty\| \leq \delta \|\theta - y\| + L \|y - Ty\|. \quad (1.8)$$

Then, T has a unique fixed point.

Theorem 1.2 ([22], p.627) *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a Banach space X and $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a weak-contraction map satisfying condition (1.8). Let $\{\theta_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ be an iterative sequence generated by the scheme (1.7) with a real control sequence $\{\xi_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ in $[0,1]$ satisfying $\sum_{k=0}^\infty \xi_k = \infty$. Then $\{\theta_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ converges to a unique point θ^* of T .*

Lemma 1 ([18], p.4) *Let $\{\beta_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ be a nonnegative sequence for which one assumes there exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, such that for all $k \geq k_0$ one has satisfied the inequality*

$$\beta_{k+1} \leq (1 - \mu_k)\beta_k + \mu_k\gamma_k, \quad (1.9)$$

where $\mu_k \in (0,1)$, for all $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $\sum_{k=0}^\infty \mu_k = \infty$ and $\gamma_k \geq 0, \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Then the following inequality holds

$$0 \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \beta_k \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_k. \quad (1.10)$$

Definition 1.3 Let $-A$ is the infinitesimal generator of a C_0 –semigroup $T(t), t \geq 0$, on a Banach space X . The function $\theta \in B$ given by

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(t) &= T(t)[\theta_0 - g(\theta)] \\ &+ \int_0^t T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds, \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

for $0 \leq t < 1$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(t) &= T(t)[\theta_0 - g(\theta)] + \int_0^1 T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds \\ &+ \int_1^t T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \theta(s-1))ds, \end{aligned} \quad (1.12)$$

for $1 \leq t \leq b$, is called the mild solution of the problem (1.4)-(1.6).

Before proceeding to the statement of our main results, we shall set forth some preliminaries and hypotheses that will be used in our subsequent discussion.

Let X be the Banach space with norm $\|\cdot\|$. Let $B = C(J, X)$ be the space of all continuous functions from J into X endowed with the supremum norm

$$\|\theta\|_B = \sup\{\|\theta(t)\| : t \in J\}.$$

I listed the following hypotheses:

H1) $-A$ is the infinitesimal generator of a semigroup of bounded linear operators $T(t)$ in X such that

$$\|T(t)\| \leq N, \forall t \in J.$$

H2) There exist $G > 0$ such that

$$\|g(\theta) - g(\bar{\theta})\| \leq G \|\theta - \bar{\theta}\|, \forall \theta, \bar{\theta} \in B.$$

H3) The function $f: J \times X \times X \times X \rightarrow X$ is continuous and there exist constant $\mathcal{L} > 0$ in (1.4) satisfies the condition

$$\|f(t, \theta, x, y) - f(t, \bar{\theta}, \bar{x}, \bar{y})\| \leq \mathcal{L}(\|\theta - \bar{\theta}\| + \|x - \bar{x}\| + \|y - \bar{y}\|), \forall \theta, \bar{\theta}, x, \bar{x}, y, \bar{y} \in X.$$

H4) There exists constant $\alpha > 0$ such that

$$\|\theta(s) - \bar{\theta}(s)\| + \|\theta(s-1) - \bar{\theta}(s-1)\| \leq 2\alpha \|\theta - \bar{\theta}\|, \forall \theta, \bar{\theta} \in B, s \in J$$

H5) $\varphi: [0, b] \times X \rightarrow X$ and there exist $\bar{Q} > 0$ such that

$$\|\psi(t, \theta) - \psi(t, \bar{\theta})\| \leq \bar{Q} \|\theta - \bar{\theta}\|, \forall \theta, \bar{\theta} \in B, s \in J$$

2 EXISTENCE AND UNIQUENESS OF SOLUTIONS VIA NEW THREE STEPS ITERATIVE METHOD

Now, we are able to state and prove the following main theorem which deals with the existence and uniqueness of solutions of the problem (1.4)-(1.6) We first prove the main conclusion.

Theorem 2.1 Assume that hypotheses (\mathcal{H}_1) - (\mathcal{H}_5) hold. Let $\{\xi_k\}_{k=0}^{\infty}$ be real sequence in $[0,1]$ satisfying $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \xi_k = \infty$ Then the equation (1.4)-(1.6) has a unique solution $\theta \in C[t_0, b]$ which is the required solution and is obtained by the three steps iterative method starting with any element $\theta_0 \in X$ Moreover, if θ_k is the k th successive approximation, then one has

$$\| \theta_{k+1} - \theta \| \leq \frac{\Omega^{2k+2}}{e^{(1-\Omega)\sum_{i=0}^k \xi_i}} \| \theta_0 - \theta \|, \quad (2.1)$$

, where $\Omega = \max\{\Omega_1, \Omega_2\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}\bar{Q}b^2, \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + 2\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b\alpha + \mathcal{N}\bar{Q}\mathcal{L}(b + b^2)\}$ and $\Omega < 1$.

Proof 2.2 Let $\theta(t) \in B$. We define the operator

Case 1 for $0 \leq t < 1$

$$\begin{aligned} F\theta(t) &= T(t)[\theta_0 - g(\theta)] \\ &+ \int_0^t T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

and **Case 2** for $1 \leq t \leq b$

$$\begin{aligned} F\theta(t) &= T(t)[\theta_0 - g(\theta)] + \int_0^1 T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds \\ &+ \int_1^t T(t-s)f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \theta(s-1))ds, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Let $\{\xi_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ be iterative sequence generated by new three steps iteration method (1.7) for the operator given in (2.2-2.3) with the real control sequence $\{\xi_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ in $[0, 1]$. We will show that $\theta_k \rightarrow \theta$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. From (1.7),(2.2),(2.3) and assumptions, we obtain

Case 1 For $0 \leq t < 1$. From the hypotheses, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\| z_k(t) - \theta(t) \| \\ &= \| (F\theta_k)(t) - (F\theta)(t) \| \\ &\leq \| T(t)[g(\theta_k) - g(\theta)] + \int_0^t T(t-s) \| f(s, \theta_k(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta_k(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds \\ &\quad - f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds \| \\ &\leq \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} \| \theta_k - \theta \| + \mathcal{N} \int_0^t \mathcal{L}(\| \theta_k - \theta \| + b\bar{Q} \| \theta_k - \theta \| + \| \phi(s) - \phi(s) \|)ds \\ &\leq (\mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b^2) \| \theta_k - \theta \| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \Omega_1 \|\theta_k - \theta\| \\ &\leq \Omega \|\theta_k - \theta\| \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

where $\Omega_1 = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b^2$ and $\Omega_1 \leq \Omega < 1$ $\|z_k - \theta\| \leq \Omega \|\theta_k - \theta\|$.

Case 2 For $1 \leq t \leq b$. From the hypotheses, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\|z_k(t) - x(t)\| \\ &= \|(F\theta_k)(t) - (F\theta)(t)\| \\ &\leq \|T(t)[g(\theta_k) - g(\theta)] + \int_0^1 T(t-s) \|f(s, \theta_k(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta_k(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s)) \\ &\quad - f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \phi(s))ds\| \\ &\quad + \int_1^t T(t-s) \|f(s, \theta_k(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta_k(\delta))d\delta, \theta_k(s-1)) \\ &\quad - f(s, \theta(s), \int_0^s \psi(s, \theta(\delta))d\delta, \theta_k(s-1))ds\| \\ &\leq \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} \|\theta_k - \theta\| + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L} \|\theta_k - \theta\| + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}(b + b^2) \|\theta_k - \theta\| \\ &\quad + \mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b(\|\theta_k(s) - \theta(s)\| + \|\theta_k(s-1) - \theta(s-1)\|) \\ &\leq (\mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + 2\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b\alpha + \mathcal{N}\bar{Q}\mathcal{L}(b + b^2)) \|\theta_k - \theta\| \\ &\leq \Omega_2 \|\theta_k - \theta\| \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

where $\Omega_2 = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G} + 2\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}b\alpha + \mathcal{N}\bar{Q}\mathcal{L}(b + b^2)$ and $\Omega_2 \leq \Omega < 1$.

$\|z_k(t) - \theta(t)\| \leq \Omega \|\theta_k - \theta\|$ where $\Omega = \max\{\Omega_1, \Omega_2\}$. Now by taking supremum in the inequality we get

$$\|z_k(t) - \theta(t)\|_B \leq \Omega \|\theta_k - \theta\|_B. \tag{2.6}$$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} &\|y_k(t) - \theta(t)\| = \|(1 - \xi_k)z_k(t) + \xi_k(Fz_k)(t) - \theta(t)\| \\ &= \|(1 - \xi_k)z_k(t) + \xi_k(Fz_k)(t) - (1 - \xi_k)\theta(t) - \xi_k\theta(t)\| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \| (1 - \xi_k)(z_k(t) - \theta(t)) + \xi_k(Fz_k)(t) - (F\theta)(t) \| \\ &\leq [(1 - \xi_k) \| z_k(t) - \theta(t) \| + \xi_k \| (Fz_k)(t) - (F\theta)(t) \|] \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Hence, by taking supremum in the inequality (2.7) and then use (2.6) to get

$$\begin{aligned} \| y_k - \theta \|_B &\leq [(1 - \xi_k) \| z_k(t) - \theta \|_B + \xi_k \| Fz_k - F\theta \|_B] \\ &\leq (1 - \xi_k) \| z_k - \theta \|_B + \xi_k \| Fz_k - F\theta \|_B \\ &\leq [1 - \xi_k(1 - \Omega)] \| z_k - \theta \|_B \\ &\leq \Omega[1 - \xi_k(1 - \Omega)] \| \theta_k - \theta \|_B \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

Therefore, using (2.6) and (2.8), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \| \theta_{k+1} - \theta \|_B &= \| Fy_k - \theta \|_B \\ &\leq \Omega \| y_k - \theta \|_B \\ &\leq \Omega^2 [1 - \xi_k(1 - \Omega)] \| \theta_k - \theta \|_B. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Thus by induction, we get Therefore

$$\| \theta_{k+1} - \theta \|_B \leq \Omega^{2k+2} \prod_{j=0}^{j=k} [1 - \xi_j(1 - \Omega)] \| \theta_0 - \theta \|_B. \quad (2.10)$$

Since $\xi_k \in [0,1] \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ the definition Ω yields,

$$\Rightarrow \Delta \xi_k < \xi_k \leq 1 \Rightarrow \xi_k(1 - \Omega) < 1, \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}. \quad (2.11)$$

From the classical analysis, we know that $1 - x \leq e^{-x}, \forall x \in [0,1]$ Hence by utilizing this fact with (2.11) in (2.10), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \| \theta_{k+1} - \theta \|_B &\leq \Omega^{2k+2} \prod_{k=0}^k \exp^{-(1-\Omega) \sum_{j=0}^k \xi_j} \| \theta_0 - \theta \|_B. \\ \| \theta_{k+1} - \theta \|_B &\leq \frac{\Omega^{2k+2}}{e^{(1-\Omega) \sum_{i=0}^k \xi_i}} \| \theta_0 - \theta \|_B. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Thus, we have proved (2.1). Since $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \xi_k = \infty$, then we have

$$e^{-(1-\Omega)\sum_{i=0}^k \xi_i} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty \quad (2.13)$$

Hence using this, the inequality (2.1) implies $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta\|_B = 0$ and therefore, we get $\theta_k \rightarrow \theta$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

Remark It is an interesting to note that the above inequality (2.1) gives the bounds in terms of known functions, which majorizes the iterations for solutions of the problem (1.4)-(1.6) for $t \in I$.

Similarly I obtained results for Continuous dependency of solution on initial data, initial function f involved therein, Continuous dependence of solution of equation on certain parameter.

3 CONCLUSION

I established the existence, uniqueness and other properties of solutions of an abstract nonlinear volterra integrodifferential equation with nonlocal condition. The tool employed in the analysis is based on application of new three steps iteration. I hope that problems on higher order integrodifferential equation will be solved in near future and will open new fields of applications.

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